

Equilibrium Studies on Binary and Ternary Complexes of Transition Metal Ions with 3-Methyl-1,2-cyclopentanedione and other Ligands in Solution

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Equilibrium studies on the formation of binary ML, ML₂ and ternary MAL complexes (where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}; A = α -alanine, valine, ethylenediamine, 2,2'-bipyridyl, catechol and oxalic acid; L = 3-methyl-1,2-cyclopentanedione) have been carried out in aqueous medium using pH-metric technique at 20, 30, 40 and 50 \pm 1° and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. The thermodynamic parameters ΔH , ΔS and ΔG associated with the binary complexes (ML) were calculated and discussed. The stabilities of ternary complexes have been discussed in terms of the basicity of ligands, nature of donor atoms, metal-ligand π -interactions, statistical aspects, change in effective charge on central metal ion, stability per unit base strength (SUBS). The distribution of different complex species present in the solution as a function of pH is illustrated for representative systems. The log K values and the percentage of species computed gave parallel evidence for stabilisation of ternary complexes.

Ternary metal complexes play an important role in various biological systems¹ and in different fields of chemistry². Hence, the formation, stability and reactivity of these complexes have been an active field of research³. In continuation of our earlier work in this field^{4,5}, we have investigated the formation of binary and ternary complexes involving 3-methyl-1,2-cyclopentanedione (MCPD), which exhibits various biological activities⁶. The MCPD exists in 100% enolic form in its aqueous solution⁷. The present communication reports the results of the studies on the binary (ML and ML₂) and ternary (MAL) complexes of MCPD (L) with the bivalent metal ions Co, Ni, Cu and Zn in presence of other ligands (A), viz. alanine (ala), valine (val), ethylenediamine (en), 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), oxalic acid (oxa) and catechol (cat) in aqueous medium at 30° and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

Binary systems : The metal-ligand binary formation constants have been evaluated by various computational techniques and linear plots. The average log K_n values along with the pK_a values of the ligands are presented in Table 1. The \bar{n} values (0.1–1.9) for the binary systems indicate the formation of 1 : 1 (ML) and 1 : 2 (ML₂) complexes. The buffer region representing complex formation

of M(II)-MCPD is at pH range 5.5–7.5. The standard deviation for all the constants reported are within \pm 0.06 log units.

In order to see the effect of temperature on stabilities of binary complexes, the proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation equilibria were studied at different temperatures. The stepwise and overall stability constants of these chelates decreased with increase in temperature indicating that the formation equilibria are exothermic and spontaneous in nature. This is also evidenced by the fact that both the free energy (ΔG) and enthalpy (ΔH) are negative. The entropy (ΔS) values are positive for the overall formation process suggests that entropy factor favours the formation of binary complexes in solution.

Ternary systems : The formation of ternary complexes was studied under the same conditions as for the binary complexes at 30°, except that the solutions contained equivalent amounts of metal and ligand solutions. The complex formation in systems such as those under study is the result of competition between metal ions and protons towards the ligands. At higher pH, the hydroxyl ions compete with the ligands for the metal ions so that hydroxo complexes are present in appreciable concentrations. The nature of the species present in

the solution is therefore highly pH-dependent. In the present study, a pH range of 4.5–9.0 has been chosen for complexation so that the protonated and hydroxyl species are kept at minimum.

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of the Cu(II)-A-L (1 : 1 : 1) ternary systems.

In the ternary systems, type MAL (where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}; A = ala, val, en, cat; L =

MCPD), the buffer region representing complex formation with the mixed ligand curve occurs at relatively lower pH compared to either ML or MA binary curve and indicates the simultaneous formation of mixed ligand complex.

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND, BINARY FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF M(II)-MCPD SYSTEMS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

Temp. = 30°, $\mu = 0.1 M$

Ligand/ Parameter	pK _a	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
ala	9.78	4.53	5.56	8.15	5.01
val	9.64	4.34	5.54	8.11	4.76
en	6.94 9.73	6.32	7.56	10.52	5.87
bipy	1.51 4.48	5.98	7.13	8.07	5.26
oxa	1.29 4.08	4.99	5.28	4.82	5.34
cat	9.25 11.54	7.47	7.67	12.32	8.32
MCPD ^a	9.11	3.76 (3.40)	3.82 (3.44)	5.45 (4.76)	4.38 (3.85)
–ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	–	15.62	15.80	18.30	18.71
–ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	–	21.81	22.16	31.61	25.41
ΔS (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	–	20.46	21.12	43.89	22.11

^aValue shown in parenthesis is log K_{ML₂}^{ML}.

The mixed ligand curves of [Cu^{II}-A-L] ternary systems closely follow those of [Cu^{II}-A] binary curves indicating that the [Cu^{II}-A] species predominates in the initial stages of complexation until the protons of primary ligands are neutralised. Before divergence of the ternary curve from the binary curve at higher pH region, there is an apparent overlap of buffer regions at lower pH in which the simple and ternary complexes are formed. Thus, the formation of mixed ligand chelates commences before the completion of the formation of the primary complex and the results of the calculations are in keeping with such an inference. In the region where the calculations are performed, the hydroxo species would be present only in negligible amounts.

In MAL ternary systems (where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}; A = 2,2'-bipy, oxa; L = MCPD) the mixed ligand curves follow those of 1 : 1 MA curve in the lower pH region of 3–5, until the protons of

2,2'-bipy and oxa are completely neutralised, indicating [M(II)-A] complex formation in this region. The deviation of the ternary curve from binary curve above this pH region results in the formation of MAL ternary complex in two-step equilibria. The formation of ternary complex can also be seen on comparison of the mixed ligand titration curve with the theoretical composite curve obtained by the graphical addition of the secondary ligand (L) titration curve to the 1 : 1 M(II)-bipy/oxa titration curve. The clear difference between them indicates the formation of a stable ternary complex species. The formation constants of ternary complexes are presented in Table 2.

The stability constants of ternary complexes are characterised by $\Delta \log K$ and these values are in accordance with statistically expected values. The $\Delta \log K$ values for M(II)-bipy-MCPD systems are found to be less negative than other related systems studied. This can be explained as follows. The ligand bipy is bound to the metal ion by N-M σ -bond, also by M-N π -bond. The $d_{\pi}-p_{\pi}$ interactions does not allow the concentration of electron density on the metal ion to increase significantly and therefore the electron repulsions are reduced to minimum. In other words, the electronegativity of the metal ion in [M-(bipy)]²⁺ is almost same as in [M_{aq}]²⁺ which facilitates stronger interaction between this complex and secondary ligand and hence less negative $\Delta \log K$ values are observed. Another explanation was extended by Griesser and

Sigel⁸ in terms of Pearson's hard and soft acid-base rule. As a result of back-donation of electrons from d -orbitals of metal ions to bipy, the metal ion becomes harder acid and this favours coordination with oxygen donor ligands. The $\Delta \log K$ values of M(II)-oxa-MCPD systems are found to be more negative than other systems containing same metal ion. Since oxalic acid is a negatively charged ligand, charge neutralisation takes place when oxa interacts with metal ion and lowers the interaction of metal ion with MCPD. Moreover, in oxa due to carboxylic oxygen the π -interaction is restricted. In addition to charge neutralisation and restriction to π -interaction, steric factors may also influence the formation of ternary complexes. Thus oxa forms less stable ternary complexes.

The stability values of M(II)-ala-MCPD systems are greater than those of M(II)-val-MCPD systems. This may be due to steric effects caused by methyl groups in valine. The stabilities of M(II)-cat-MCPD systems are higher than that of M(II)-oxa-MCPD systems and this order is in accordance with their basicities. A direct correlation of complex stabilities, however, could not be made, since the basicities of these ligands are not of the same order. The base strength is a measure of the σ -bonding ability of the ligands with the metal ion. Therefore, such a direct comparison of the stabilities would not throw any light on the factors like π -bonding, steric and chelate effects. The stability per unit base strength (SUBS)⁹ can give rational explanation to overcome such difficulties.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS, $\Delta \log K$ AND SUBS VALUES OF (1 : 1 : 1) TERNARY SYSTEMS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM*

Ligand (A)	Co ^{II}			Ni ^{II}			Cu ^{II}			Zn ^{II}		
	$\log \beta_{MAL}^M$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	$\log \beta_{MAL}^M$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	$\log \beta_{MAL}^M$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	$\log \beta_{MAL}^M$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS
ala	7.80	-0.49	0.413	8.95	-0.43	0.473	13.23 (5.08)	-0.37	0.700	8.92	-0.47	0.472
val	7.59	-0.51	0.405	8.91	-0.45	0.475	13.17 (5.06)	-0.39	0.702	8.63	-0.51	0.460
en	9.62	-0.46	0.373	10.99	-0.39	0.426	15.63 (5.11)	-0.34	0.606	9.82	-0.43	0.381
bipy	9.35 (3.37)	-0.39	0.619	10.61 (3.48)	-0.34	0.702	13.23 (5.16)	-0.29	0.876	9.28 (4.02)	-0.36	0.614
oxa	8.09 (3.10)	-0.66	0.570	8.51 (3.23)	-0.59	0.600	9.73 (4.91)	-0.54	0.686	9.09 (3.75)	-0.63	0.641
cat	10.65	-0.58	0.356	11.01	-0.48	0.368	17.37 (5.05)	-0.40	0.581	12.14	-0.56	0.406

* Value in parenthesis is $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$

The order of overall stabilities ($\log \beta_{MAL}^M$) is $cat > en > bipy > ala > val > oxa$ and the order of SUBS is $bipy > oxa > ala > val > en > cat$.

From the Table 2 it can be seen that although the stabilities of M(II)-cat-MCPD systems are greater than M(II)-oxa-MCPD systems, the SUBS values greater for the latter systems may be due to extended chelation. The SUBS values for M(II)-bipy-MCPD higher than M(II)-en-MCPD systems, may be due to more π -bonding ability in addition to extended chelation.

It can be seen that binary complexes are more stable than the ternary complexes resulting a negative $\Delta \log K$ values in all the ternary systems studied. Such a lowering of stabilities of ternary complexes compared to that of binary chelates may be due to the greater destabilisation effects¹⁰ caused by the ligand repulsions in mixed ligand complexes than that in the binary systems, coupled with the availability of lesser number of coordinating sites for second ligand on the primary complex $[M(II)-A]$ compared to free $[M^{2+}]_{aq}$ ions.

In order to understand the coordination behaviour of metal ions with ligands, it is of interest to examine some details of species diagram to represent the distribution of various species present in the solution as a percentage of metal ion concentration and their variation with pH. The distribution curves for representative species are given for Cu(II)-ala-MCPD and Cu(II)-en-MCPD systems in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the pH regions of complexation for Cu-ala/en are 3–5.5 and 3.5–5.5 respectively, and for Cu-MCPD it is above 5. Hence the ligands interact in stepwise manner for the formation of the corresponding ternary complex. Here the concentrations of Cu(II)-ala/en-MCPD reaches a maximum of 92% of total copper at pH 9.5. At lower pH region the Cu-ala/en complex is the major species present. The extent to which the mixed ligand complexes formed depends not only on the relative and absolute concentrations of the metal ion and ligands that are present, but also on the relevant pK_a and stability constant values as well as on the pH of the solution. In M(II)-bipy-MCPD system, though bipy is a π -acceptor ligand, which would enhance the interaction of metal ion with secondary ligand, the formation of ternary

complex is just 40%, indicating the influence of statistical factors on the formation of ternary complex. In oxalic acid system, where oxa acts as a primary ligand and MCPD acts as secondary ligand, the formation of ternary species is about 40%.

The order of stability constants of ternary complexes with respect to metal ions is $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$. This order is in agreement with the Irving-Williams¹¹ (natural) order.

Experimental

The ligand MCPD (Aldrich) was used. All other chemicals used were of A.R. (B.D.H.) grade. The pH-metric titrations of the binary systems were carried out at 20, 30, 40 and $50 \pm 1^\circ$ and that of ternary systems at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. In all the cases an ionic strength of 0.1 M (KNO_3) was maintained. The general experimental procedures employed were similar to those described earlier⁴, except the change in concentration of some solutions as follows: (i) $HNO_3 = 2 \times 10^{-3} M$, (ii) $M(II) = A = L = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ for ternary systems, and (iii) $M(II) = 2 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $L = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$ for binary systems.

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants of binary systems were determined by Irving-Rossotti¹² technique. The ternary formation constants were evaluated using known expressions¹³ by analysing the titration curves with the help of suitable computer programmes on a CASIO-PB-110 computer. Various models were fitted to the data and the model selected was that which gave the best statistical fit. The proton-ligand dissociation constants (pK_a) and binary stability constants of all other ligands (A) were redetermined under present experimental conditions and were found to be in good agreement with the values reported earlier⁵. The thermodynamic parameters ΔS , ΔH and ΔG were calculated using known equations. In order to have uniformity and better correlation, stepwise formation constants were converted into simultaneous formation constants ($\log \beta_{MAL}^M$)¹⁴. BEST¹⁵ computer program was used to generate the complete species distribution curves (Fig. 1) at various pH values.

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